

STAGES OF MANAGEMENT DECISION-MAKING IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the stages of making managerial decisions when starting a business. These decisions contain important concepts in business activities and cover many topics such as innovations, dealing with international companies, and the issue of trade protection. The article consists of five stages, including the journey of writing ideas and articles in entrepreneurial activity, business development strategy, business planning strategy, marketing strategy, choosing a strategy for working with employees and trade opponents, specializing with partners and foreign organizations, room and construction viewing and equipment organization topics are shown.

Keywords: entrepreneurs, purpose, organization, legal entity, strategy preparation, adding resources, reliable team.

Making management decisions when starting a business consists of the following stages:

Case study and evaluation

Before starting a business, it is necessary to study and evaluate the situation of the entrepreneur. At this stage, entrepreneurs need to gather explanatory data, economic analysis, and customer information to get the most out of compliance. [1]

Defining goals: After the goals that the management should set for the establishment of the business activity are protected, the entrepreneurs issue new strategies with the goals of watching and supporting.

Perfecting the organizational structure: One of the important stages of starting a business is the classification of the organizational structure, the services of representatives, and the appointment of management by employees. It delivers customization when entrepreneurs use metrics from multiple base managers.[2]

Communicate a lot of information with management and employees: Entrepreneurs require a lot of information exchange between managers and employees to ensure long-term bonding between employees and couples. The fact that they have studied ongoing promotions, most entrepreneurs are faced with professional development.

New direction and goals: In setting up an entrepreneurial activity, the narrative parts of the events, and the consultants setting new goals in the time spent on the original events, the entrepreneurs get the base lot in compliance. With this privatization, entrepreneurs can make changes to the Partnership for Change if they want to.[3]

To make reliable goals real and practical, it is necessary to create legal entities and make decisions about them at the first stage of business regulation.

For this purpose, the following should be done:

1. Determination of directions of entrepreneurial activity, identification of service or product-oriented to entrepreneurial activity.

2. With the help of the latest legal and non-legal indicators, it is necessary to put the necessary types of legal entities and education and qualification specialists in their activities.

3. It is necessary to follow the rules on the structure of legal entities. Based on the learning process, legal entities should be created by the procurement processes, departments, and categories of employees in the enterprise.

4. To regulate the activities of legal entities, it is necessary to assign and deposit initial capital in the necessary amounts.

5. To verify that the person has fully completed the study of governmental abilities to create the legal structure recommended for regulation.

6. Stages related to the provision of legal signs, services, or products to a person, the implementation of business activities and sidqi business chambers, legal and financial issues, or the main development procedure.[4]

The form, organization, creation, and activity of legal entities allow us to observe productive changes from the amount of the award.

It helps to decide on the establishment of a system of monitoring and control of the practical and financial condition of the business activity, to assess the sincere financial condition, development, and prospects of the business activity. For this purpose, the following steps should be taken to make a decision:

1. Preparation of financial statements: Annual, quarterly, and other financial statements of enterprises should be defined.

2. Ensuring financial control: checking the financial calculations and processes of enterprises, identifying errors in them, correcting them, and directly registering them.

3. Objectives and obligations of enterprises in the quarter: to compile a list of enterprises in the state of cooperation in the quarter and to determine all obligations and objectives.

4. Customer Service Needed Actions: Define several customer service business concepts, promotional strategies, and clear acceptable metrics for customer service times.

5. Checking the quality of financial documents: preparing financial documents (documents) of enterprises and checking their authenticity and content with natural indicators.

6. Identification of enterprise errors and correction of identified errors: identification of errors made under enterprise management, their elimination, and prevention of any repetition.

7. Solution of issues of a financial and legal nature, as well as maintenance of developed financial instructions.

It is important to establish a system of monitoring and controlling the practice and financial status of business activities, to ensure that the financial and legal requirements and obligations of enterprises do not deteriorate in their basic state.[5]

CONCLUSION

Making management decisions when starting a business has a major impact on the success of the business. Practices such as setting goals, preparing a strategy, adding resources, creating a reliable team, creating a monitoring system and finding the necessary funds for business development, attracting emigration funds are accepted. These are the only actions for all entrepreneurs and are one of their independent steps towards business development and great success.

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